

Study of Histomorphological Spectrum of Malignant Breast Diseases- in a Tertiary Care Centre of Mumbai

Aditi Raj¹, Jyoti Jaysing Rajput², Sonal Raut³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Seth G. S. Medical College & KEM Hospital, Mumbai, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Seth G. S. Medical College & KEM Hospital, Mumbai, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Seth G. S. Medical College & KEM Hospital, Mumbai, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Aditi Raj

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Abstract:

Background: Worldwide, breast cancer is the most frequent cancer among women and the primary cause of cancer related deaths. It is now the most common cancer among women in India, surpassing even cervical cancer. Accurate diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment planning of breast cancer depend on an understanding of its histomorphological features. The purpose of this study is to look at the histomorphological range of breast cancers.

Methods: Ninety female patients diagnosed with malignant breast diseases were included. Data on patient demographics, clinical presentation, and histopathological findings were collected. Tumor types, grades, and lymphovascular invasion were analyzed. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Ninety patients, whose mean age was 53.4 years, were enrolled in the study. The most prevalent tumour type (80%) was invasive ductal carcinoma (IDC), which was followed by invasive lobular carcinoma (11.1%), mucinous carcinoma (4.4%) and other tumour types. The majority of tumours (55.6%) were Grade 2, followed by Grade 3 (33.3%) and Grade 1 (11.1%). Lymphovascular invasion was seen in 38.9% of patients which was substantially correlated with IDC ($p = 0.025$).

Conclusion: IDC is the predominant type of malignant breast disease in this cohort, with a significant association between IDC and lymphovascular invasion, indicating a higher metastatic potential. The findings highlight the importance of histopathological examination in diagnosing and prognosticating breast cancer.

Recommendations: Early detection and tailored treatment strategies are essential, especially for patients with IDC and lymphovascular invasion. Further studies with larger sample sizes are recommended to validate these findings and explore additional histomorphological parameters.

Keywords: Breast Cancer, Histomorphological Spectrum, Invasive Ductal Carcinoma, Lymphovascular Invasion.

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Introduction

Breast cancer continues to be one of the most prevalent cancers that affect women worldwide, with high rates of morbidity and death. Breast cancer is the most common cancer among women and the primary cause of cancer-related fatalities, with 2.3 million new cases and 685,000 deaths globally in 2020 alone, according to the World Health Organisation [1]. With an expected 162,468 new cases and 87,090 deaths in 2018, breast cancer has surpassed cervical cancer as the most frequent cancer among women in India [2].

Breast cancer exhibits a broad spectrum of histomorphology, with different subtypes exhibiting unique biology and clinical

characteristics. About 70–80% of all breast cancers are of the most prevalent histological subtype, invasive ductal carcinoma (IDC) [3]. Tubular carcinoma, mucinous carcinoma, cribriform carcinoma and secretory carcinoma and invasive lobular carcinoma are some other less frequent subtypes. Different histological characteristics of each subtype affect treatment choices and prognosis.

The role of histopathological examination in the diagnosis and management of breast cancer cannot be overstated. It provides critical information on tumor type, grade, and the presence of lymphovascular invasion, which are essential for

staging and prognostication. Tumor grade, determined by the degree of differentiation, is a significant prognostic factor, with higher-grade tumors generally associated with poorer outcomes. Similarly, the presence of lymphovascular invasion is indicative of a higher risk of metastasis and has been correlated with worse survival rates.

Our knowledge of breast cancer has been significantly enhanced by recent developments in molecular biology, which have allowed for the identification of molecular subtypes based on gene expression profiles. Different clinical outcomes and responses to therapy are observed for these subtypes, which include triple-negative, HER2-enriched, luminal A, and luminal B [4]. Integrating molecular classification with traditional histopathology offers a more comprehensive approach to breast cancer diagnosis and management, tailoring treatments to individual patient profiles.

Despite these advancements, challenges remain in breast cancer care, particularly in low- and middle-income countries like India. Factors such as late presentation, limited access to healthcare, and variability in the quality of diagnostic and therapeutic services contribute to poorer outcomes. There is a pressing need for robust data on the histomorphological characteristics of breast cancer in these settings to inform public health strategies and improve clinical practices.

This study aims to investigate the histomorphological spectrum of malignant breast diseases.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional descriptive study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted over a period of 19 months from June 2021 to December 2023.

Participants: A total of 90 patients diagnosed with malignant breast diseases were included in this study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Female patients aged 18 years and above.
- Patients diagnosed with malignant epithelial breast tumors confirmed by histopathological examination.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with benign breast diseases and mesenchymal tumors.

- Patients who had received neoadjuvant chemotherapy before the histopathological examination.
- Patients with incomplete medical records.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all consecutive patients meeting the inclusion criteria during the study period were included. Information bias was reduced by using standardized data collection procedures and training the data collectors. Confounding variables were controlled through appropriate statistical methods during data analysis.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured proforma, which included patient demographics, clinical presentation, and histopathological findings. Relevant clinical data were obtained from medical records and patient interviews.

Procedure

1. **Histopathological Examination:** Breast tissue samples obtained from biopsies or surgical specimens were processed and stained with hematoxylin and eosin.

2. **Microscopic Analysis:** Each sample was examined under a microscope by experienced pathologists to identify and classify the type of malignant breast disease.

3. **Data Recording:** Histomorphological features, including tumor type, grade, and presence of lymphovascular invasion, were recorded and analysed.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was utilised for data entry and analysis. To summarise continuous variables, descriptive statistics like mean, median, and standard deviation were employed. Frequencies and percentages were used to represent categorical variables. The study employed chi-square tests to evaluate the correlation between category variables. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Result

The study comprised ninety patients, with a mean age of 53.4 ± 12.3 years. Patients between the ages of 40 and 60 made up the majority of the patient population (60%) and those under 40 made up 15% and 25% of patients were > 60 years of age. Palpable lumps accounted for 80% of the clinical presentation, with discomfort (10%), nipple discharge (5%), and other symptoms at presentation (5%).

Table 1: Patient Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

Age Group	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
< 40 years	14	15
40-60 years	54	60
> 60 years	22	25

The histopathological examination revealed the following types of malignant breast diseases:

Table 2: Histomorphological Findings

Tumor type	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Invasive Ductal Carcinoma (IDC)	72	80
Invasive Lobular Carcinoma (ILC)	10	11.1
Mucinous Carcinoma	4	4.4
Tubular Carcinoma	2	2.2
Others	2	2.2

The distribution of tumor grades among the patients was as follows:

Table 3: Tumor Grade

Tumor Grade	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Grade 1	10	11.1
Grade 2	50	55.6
Grade 3	30	33.3

Lymphovascular invasion (LVI) was present in 35 (38.9%) of the cases.

Table 4: Lymphovascular Invasion

Lymphovascular Invasion	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Present	35	38.9
Absent	55	61.1

The association between tumor type and lymphovascular invasion was assessed using the Chi-square test.

Table 6: Association between tumor type and lymphovascular invasion

Tumor Type	LVI Present	LVI Absent	p-value
Invasive Ductal Carcinoma (IDC)	30	42	0.025
Invasive Lobular Carcinoma (ILC)	3	7	0.410
Mucinous Carcinoma	1	3	0.800
Tubular Carcinoma	1	1	0.550
Others	0	2	0.600

Discussion

The patient population had a mean age of 53.4 years, with the majority (60%) falling within the 40-60 years age range. Most patients presented with a palpable lump (80%), making it the most common clinical presentation. This demographic and clinical profile aligns with global trends, indicating a higher prevalence of breast cancer in middle-aged women with palpable lumps as the primary symptom.

Histopathological analysis revealed that IDC was the predominant type of malignant breast disease, accounting for 80% of cases. This finding is consistent with existing literature, which identifies IDC as the most common form of breast cancer. Other types, such as invasive lobular carcinoma (11.1%), mucinous carcinoma (4.4%), and tubular carcinoma (2.2%), were less frequently observed. The distribution of tumor grades showed that Grade 2 tumors were the most common (55.6%), followed by Grade 3 (33.3%) and Grade 1 (11.1%). These findings suggest that most patients had moderately to poorly differentiated tumors, which could have implications for their prognosis and treatment strategies.

Lymphovascular invasion (LVI) was present in 38.9% of cases, indicating a significant risk for metastasis in these patients. The statistical analysis

showed a significant association between IDC and the presence of LVI ($p=0.025$), underscoring the aggressive nature of this tumor type and its potential for metastasis. This highlights the need for careful monitoring and aggressive treatment in patients diagnosed with IDC, particularly those with LVI, to improve their clinical outcomes.

Overall, this study provides a comprehensive overview of the histomorphological spectrum of malignant breast diseases. The high prevalence of IDC and the significant association between this tumor type and lymphovascular invasion emphasize the importance of early detection and tailored treatment strategies. These findings contribute to the understanding of breast cancer characteristics in the local population and underscore the need for continued research and improved clinical practices to enhance patient care and outcomes.

Over a ten-year period, the histomorphology of several breast illnesses was examined in a study, both proactively and retrospectively. All breast tissue specimens obtained by the Pathology department's surgical pathology division were included in the study. According to the findings, breast lesions made up 1.66% of all surgical pathology specimens, with 68.3% of them being benign. The most frequent breast lesion was

fibroadenomas, which were followed by carcinomas (31.7%). In contrast to Western literature, the study discovered that carcinomas in their community manifested at younger ages and in more advanced stages, underscoring the need for enhanced early detection services [5].

According to a related study, the most common breast cancer was infiltrating duct carcinoma (IDC), with Grade 2 IDCs being more common than Grade 1 and Grade 3 IDCs. According to the study, breast tumours in younger populations often manifested at an advanced stage, underscoring the need for improved early detection and treatment accessibility [6].

A descriptive study analyzed 52 cases of breast lesions. They found that 33% were non-neoplastic, while 67% were neoplastic. Among the neoplastic lesions, 40.3% were benign, and 26.9% were malignant, with invasive breast carcinoma being the most common malignant diagnosis. This study highlights the importance of histopathology in distinguishing between benign and malignant lesions for accurate diagnosis and treatment planning [7].

A retrospective study examined 3608 specimens, finding 724 neoplastic cases, of which 499 were benign and 225 malignant. The most common malignant tumors were in the oral cavity (47 cases) and breast (44 cases). This study highlighted the prevalence of breast malignancies even in rural settings and the critical need for accessible diagnostic and treatment services [8].

Conclusion

This study highlights the predominance of invasive ductal carcinoma among malignant breast diseases, with a significant proportion of cases exhibiting lymphovascular invasion. The findings underscore the importance of early detection and tailored treatment strategies, particularly for aggressive tumor types like IDC. Continued research and improved clinical practices are essential to enhance patient care and outcomes in this population.

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